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D3.1 Report on contextually sensitive framework for defining QRPs

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Executive summary

Questionable Research Practices (henceforth, QRPs) are a foundational concept in research integrity, but also fraught with inherent ambiguities. They are by definition a grey area of practices that may or may not be problematic depending on the context, and for this reason are hard to define, quantify and study. One of the core tasks of WP3 was to address these limitations, by offering a theoretical framework to better define and contextualise QRPs, and empirically assess the possible effects of the identified contextual features.

This deliverable reports the results of three studies that met these objectives. These studies are currently under review or in preparation, and this report presents an excerpt and synthesis of them.

The first study collected the definitions of QRPs from surveys about research misconduct, and reclassified these definitions according to a principled scheme. Results yield 27 distinctive types of QRP and show that the QRPs most commonly self-reported in surveys consists in either the selective reporting of data, covariates, analyses, results, and publications, or in HARKing, a QRP in which hypotheses obtained after viewing the results are presented as being tested and confirmed by those results. These QRP are also the most context-sensitive, and thus constituted the basis for the second and third study.

The second study produced a framework to contextualise QRPs. This was based on Information Compression Theory (ICT), a theoretical framework that proposes to understand metascientific problems through the lenses of information theory. Focusing on QRPs that (1) introduce bias in a study and (2) are not fully reported in the study, the ICT analysis suggests that a QRP study is most likely to affect the literature, positively or negatively, in fields that have a high information yield (e.g. fields characterised by simpler phenomena and more mature methods), high replicability (e.g. fields characterised by greater transparency and greater codification of methods) and higher biases (e.g. fields in which studies already systematically over- or underestimate the result, due to QRPs). These three dimensions, and the possible factors that affect them, constituted the basis for the third study included in this report.

The third study aimed at assessing if and how researchers take contextual factors into account when evaluating the severity of a QRP. Focusing on HARKing as a common and context-sensitive QRP, we conducted a randomised online experiment in which researchers were shown a vignette reporting a fictitious study and were asked to express their preference between two summaries, one of which embodied HARKing. Five dimension of context were manipulated. Results show that researchers on average rated the non-questionable summary higher, and that none of the five contextual factors significantly modulated their judgement. However, researchers who believed that these contextual factors were important for evaluating a QRP judged the HARKing vignette less negatively.

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List of Abbreviations

QRP: questionable research practices.

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1 A Principled Classification and Ranking of Questionable Research Practices Based on Survey Data

The notion of “Questionable Research Practice” (QRP, also referred to as “unacceptable practices” ALLEA 2023) is central to the research integrity agenda and yet eludes clear definition and measurement. On the one hand, QRPs are more common than outright scientific misconduct (i.e. Fabrication, Falsification, and Plagiarism (FFP)) and are believed to be potentially just as damaging in aggregate and therefore an important source of bias and reproducibility problems that need to be tackled with special training, incentives and punishments (e.g. Bouter 2023). On the other hand, it is also well understood that QRPs are by definition a “grey area” of behaviours that may constitute valid practices in some contexts and invalid in others. Indeed, the intrinsic difficulty in defining and demarcating QRPs generates considerable uncertainty and controversy about their actual prevalence and impact (e.g. Fiedler and Schwarz 2016).

Formal classifications of QRP have been proposed in the literature (e.g. Steneck and Zinn 2004, Hall and Martin 2019, Manapat et al. 2024), but these are typically coarse-grained classifications that lack the ability to capture the diversity of practices that are typically of interest to research, education, or policy-making on QRP. The difficulty of devising clear and non-arbitrary definitions of QRPs translates into even greater difficulties in estimating the true prevalence and impact of such problematic behaviours, as it impedes accurate and sufficiently fine-grained comparisons between studies (see Fanelli 2009, Xie et al. 2021).

This task aimed at overcoming this limitation in the literature by pooling survey data into a data-driven but also principled classification scheme. Specifically, we had three main objectives: 1) Document the practices that surveys on QRPs have attempted to measure; 2) Organize the definitions of QRPs given in these surveys into a set of mutually exclusive and internally consistent categories; 3) Summarize data on the prevalence of each resulting category of QRPs, pooling data across surveys.

Our central aim was to produce an adequately fine-grained and theoretically meaningful classification of QRPs that overcomes the limitations of previously proposed taxonomies. To this end, we centred our classification approach around the concept of information, which has been applied to other meta-scientific problems with encouraging results (e.g. Fanelli 2019, Fanelli et al. 2022). In particular, we posited that a research practice is questionable to the extent that it entails either the omission, the addition, or the manipulation of information, where information is intended in the broadest possible sense of any “difference that makes a difference” (Bateson 1972) - that is, any element presented in a study that makes a difference to what the study communicates to a given field of research, either directly (e.g. data, methods, interpretation) or indirectly (e.g. authorship, acknowledgments, COI).

1.1

Methods

We searched the Web of Science Core Collection database for studies that met the following criteria:

- 1 The study is about practices explicitly defined with the phrase “questionable research practices” or the acronym QRP.
- 2 The study reports original data (i.e., is not a review or meta-analysis).
- 3 The data were collected via a survey (i.e., a questionnaire administered to respondents).
- 4 The survey included questions that asked how often the respondents had engaged in specific behaviours.

This searched yielded a preliminary list of $n=72$ unique records. Inspection of their abstracts identified 48 potentially relevant studies of which the PDF was retrieved. Inspection of the PDF led to a final list of 20 studies that were included in the analysis. Screening was conducted by two researchers (AV and SA) and validated by a third (DF).

From each potentially relevant question about QRPs in each of the included studies, we recorded the text of each question *verbatim*, the formulation of the question itself, the percentage of respondents who reported engaging in the corresponding QRP at least once, and other study and question characteristics.

1.2

Results

The final sample size comprised 296 QRP data points, obtained from 23 separate samples, collected in 20 published studies.

To arrive at a classification of QRP in a set of mutually exclusive and sufficiently homogeneous categories, we proceeded inductively and iteratively. In particular, we initially developed and applied two intuitive and distinctive classification dimensions, which helped give a preliminary simplifying structure to the QRP questions. Firstly, we classified the QRP by the aspect of research practice they pertained to (i.e. Methods, Data, Analysis, Results, etc... see Figure 1 for the full list). Secondly, we classified the behaviours in each aspect according to three simple and objective qualifiers reflecting the nature of the misrepresentation of information:

- Omission: the QRP definition entails concealing relevant information (e.g. dropping data point or covariates from an analysis, or avoiding to cite contrary evidence).
- Addition: the QRP definition entails adding information (e.g. running a new analysis post-hoc, or gifting authorship).
- Modification: the QRP definition entails that information was actively modified (e.g. improperly rounding-down a P-value, or misreporting one's methods).
- Other/na: A few QRP that were not easily classifiable as any of the above categories (e.g. misappropriating research resources).

From this initial 2-dimensional classification, a set of adequately homogeneous and mutually exclusive typologies of QRP could be more easily identified. This classification identified a total of 30 categories: 27 QRP categories plus an FFP category for outright misconduct (i.e. fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism), and two categories, "other, ethics" and "other", to collect the remaining, heterogeneous behaviours. The 27 QRP categories we identified are:

1. select analysis (selectively reporting analyses of one's data)
2. select citation (selectively citing the literature)
3. select covariates (selectively including or excluding covariates in a regression analysis)
4. general p-hacking (i.e. adopting various practices that increase the risk of reporting a statistical false positive)
5. withhold methods (selectively sharing or reporting details of the methods of a study)
6. HARKing (acronym for Hypothesising After Results are Known, i.e. presenting a study as if it was testing an hypothesis that was in reality formulated post-hoc, see Kerr 1998)
7. inadequate methods

8. select results (selectively presenting the results of a study)
9. select publication (selectively publishing studies)
10. gift authorship (granting undeserved authorship)
11. select data (selectively dropping data from one's sample)
12. round p-value (improperly rounding down P-values to increase their apparent significance)
13. ignore QRP (ignoring known issues in a study)
14. ignore IRB (conducting a study without approval from an ethics committee)
15. misuse citation (citing studies inaccurately)
16. optional stop (optionally stopping the collection of data once statistical significance is reached)
17. salami-slicing (subdividing the results of a project to the minimal publishable unit)
18. misreport methods (inaccurately reporting study methods)
19. conceal limitations (of one's study)
20. gain authorship (request and/or accept gift authorship)
21. appropriate ideas (presenting ideas of others as one's own)
22. modify data
23. appropriate results (presenting results of others as one's own)
24. self-plagiarism
25. sponsor pressure (changing results to accommodate the expectations of the study's funder)
26. deny authorship
27. conceal COI (conflicts of interests).

Most of these categories corresponded to one research aspect, but some categories could span more than one aspect, due to the particular phrasing of the QRP. Similarly, some behaviours whose definitions entailed different actions (e.g. omitting vs modifying) were deemed sufficiently similar to be recombined into a single QRP category.

Ranking QRP by frequency

Figure 1 shows each QRP category, coloured by the corresponding aspect and ordered by the median of the reported percentages. This ordering suggests that the most commonly reported QRPs include selectively choosing the analysis or covariates within the analysis, selectively citing sources, withholding methodological details and HARKing. At the other extreme of the spectrum, we find FFP (i.e. behaviours that would qualify as scientific misconduct), concealing COIs, and denying authorship. Substantially similar rankings were obtained using the mean instead of the median (Figure 2, red triangles).

1.3

Discussion

Due to the high heterogeneity of the data, the validity of the numerical estimates of each QRP are dubious. However, the overall ranking observed seemed robust to secondary analyses, suggesting that the relative rank ordering of QRP shown in Figure 2 is valid and in need of explanation. We suggest that this ranking can be ascribed to three contributing factors:

1. Omission vs commission: the most frequently reported QRPs tend to be the ones that entail omission, rather than modification or addition of information, across research aspect (Fig 1). This result aligns with experiments suggesting that lying by omission is generally perceived to be less ethically problematic than lying by commission (van Swol et al. 2022), which entails that these QRPs might be engaged with (and/or

reported) more frequently because they are perceived as less ethically problematic. It also validates the assumptions of past theoretical models that equated QRP with lying by omission and misconduct with commission (Gall and Maniadis 2019).

2. **Boundary arbitrariness:** some of the highly reported QRPs have arbitrary or subjective boundaries. For example, the dividing line between legitimate authorship and Gift Authorship (i.e. having made an insufficient contribution to the study to deserve authorship) is in many cases subjective and influenced by field and cultural conventions.
3. **Ethical ambiguity:** many of the highly reported QRPs tend to be the ones whose problematic nature is most ambiguous and context-dependent. In particular, theoretical and empirical studies suggest that, under specific conditions, practices such as HARKing and selectively publishing results may have a neutral or even net positive impact on research progress (Rubin 2017; de Winter and Happee 2013). Similar arguments may be advanced for the selective reporting of analyses, selectively citing the literature and other QRPs that our analysis suggests are most common.

Therefore, results of this analysis suggest that some of the most commonly reported QRPs also tend to be the most context-dependent. In order to accurately characterise the gravity and impact of any given QRP and to devise effective interventions to improve research integrity, it is necessary to characterise the context in which they operate.

Figure 1: QRP categories and their reported frequency. The QRP categories identified, ordered by inverse frequency with which they are reported in surveys. Boxplots show median, interquartile range and outliers. QRPs are coloured by aspect or research they are relevant to, and are ordered by decreasing median reported frequency. Red triangles show the corresponding mean value. Numbers at the bottom of the graph report the number of surveys (and therefore data points in the boxplot) that yielded data for each category.

2 A theoretical framework to evaluate the epistemic impact of Questionable Research Practices

The potential of QRPs to distort research, combined with the relatively high frequency with which scientists report engaging with at least some of them, has led to widespread concerns that QRPs are a significant threat to scientific knowledge, possibly as important or more important than outright scientific misconduct (e.g. Bouter 2023). Against this view however, two main arguments have been advanced.

The first argument questions whether QRPs are really as prevalent as suggested, given that the numerous surveys upon which prevalence estimates are based struggle to draw a clear distinction between legitimate and problematic behaviour, which logically entails that surveys over-estimate the prevalence of behaviours that actually generate biases in research findings (Fiedler and Schwarz 2016).

The second, more controversial argument questions whether QRPs, even when correctly characterised, are truly always harmful to scientific progress. For example, several authors have argued that the amply documented publication bias against null or negative results might be beneficial because, if on the one hand it contributes to a "file-drawer" problem by depriving the literature of a genuine result, on the other hand it prevents a complementary "cluttered office" problem, by reducing the volume of uninformative or uninteresting literature (Silvertown and McConway 1997, de Winter and Happee 2013). Similarly, it has been argued that certain forms of undisclosed HARKing (Hypothesising After Results are Known, see Table 1) might be a positive force upon balance, at least when the post-hoc hypothesis is derived independently of the data and/or with sufficient logical and empirical rigour, because these conditions minimise the risk of bias whilst maintaining the HARKing benefit of presenting findings concisely and effectively (Rubin 2017, Vancouver 2018).

Other commonly reported QRPs identified in section 1 may also conceivably take forms that are not harmful (Table 1). Indeed, it may be argued that several practices that are deemed to be QRPs could in reality represent optimal strategies to conduct science under conditions of high complexity and large methodological limitations - conditions that are typically encountered, for example, in psychological science (Sanbonmatsu et al. 2020).

Therefore, we aimed to develop a theoretical framework to define the conditions that make a QRP more or less problematic. The key objective is to contextualise the harmfulness of QRPs by quantifying the effects that a QRP-affected study may have on the knowledge produced by a field - where by "field" we mean a literature of studies all addressing the same research question.

The analysis builds on a framework that proposes to analyse metascientific questions in terms of information compression (Fanelli 2019), and focuses on data and results-related QRPs, because these QRPs have been the principal concern of research on research integrity and because, unlike breaches of ethics and other non-data related QRPs, they by definition directly affect the reliability of scientific knowledge. The full mathematical analysis was elaborated in a paper that is currently under review, and here below we report its key conclusions.

Since our theoretical framework is concerned with properties of knowledge, our analysis focuses on QRPs that are directly related to data or results. These also happen to be the most commonly reported QRPs in surveys, as our review of the literature showed. Ethical breaches and other non-data related QRPs are not directly addressed by this analysis. Similarly, it must be emphasised that this analysis does not concern itself with principled moral implications of engaging in QRPs and focuses solely on their epistemic consequences.

Table 1: Examples of the contextual nature of QRPs. Five of the most commonly reported QRPs according to the analysis in section 1, with a general definition, and forms of it that are unequivocally harmful or non-harmful.

QRP name	Definition	Harmful	Non-harmful
Select Data	Remove data from analysis without reporting it.	Remove data after seeing the results, in order to increase their significance.	Remove outliers and highly influential points to reduce bias.
Select Covariates	Remove covariates from an analysis without reporting it.	Covariates are removed after seeing the results, in order to increase the significance of retained covariates.	Covariates are removed to avoid multicollinearity and spurious results.
Select Analysis	Report only a subset of the analyses conducted.	Analyses are selected based on whether they support a desired results.	Analyses are excluded because they are redundant, flawed or uninformative.
Select Results	Report only a subset of the results obtained.	Results are suppressed because they are unfavourable to a desired outcome, or in order to multiply publications.	Results are excluded because they are redundant or irrelevant to the intended publication.
Select Publication	Publish only a subset of the studies conducted.	Publication is limited to studies with favourable or desirable conclusions.	Publication is avoided for redundant, flawed or uninformative studies.
HARKing	Report a hypothesis derived after seeing the results as if the study was designed to test it.	Hypothesis is formulated idiosyncratically, in order to fit the results observed.	Hypothesis is theoretically sound independently of results, e.g. it is found in the literature.

2.1

Characteristics of a Questionable Research Practice

Following common definitions and examples offered in the literature, this analysis builds on the assumption that a results-related QRP possesses one or both of these characteristics:

1. Potentially introduces arbitrariness and bias: a QRP may be performed out of ignorance for its negative epistemic consequences, and yet it is "questionable" because it breaks with standards that are known and usually widely adopted by the relevant scientific community (that is, the field of literature to which the study contributes). Typically, such standards are set in place to avoid systematic errors and/or the expression of conscious or unconscious biases.

2. Not transparently reported: The questionable components are not adequately described in the publication, hampering the ability of others to properly assess the validity and importance of the findings reported.

Criterion n.2 is not universally accepted: some authors include in the definition of QRP behaviours that may introduce bias even though they are transparently reported (e.g. "Transparent Harking", Hollenbeck and Wright 2016). However, this analysis takes a different view and posits that "transparent QRP" is a contradiction in terms. Few studies, if any, are free from any errors and biases, and their scientific rigour is expressed in how transparently these limitations are communicated. The same logic must apply to QRPs: if a study produces a potentially biased result, but it transparently communicates all the conditions and actions that (may have) generated a bias in the results, then it is ethically on a par with all other studies. Because other researchers who are evaluating the relevance of the study's results are given the necessary information to account and adjust for potential distortions and therefore, at least in principle, the problem is correcting (e.g. Fanelli 2013).

2.2

Theoretical background: Information Compression Theory

Information Compression Theory (ICT, in previous studies also referred to as "K" theory) is a general framework to study and analyse meta-scientific problems (Fanelli 2019). The core assumption of ICT is that knowledge is best understood as a form of information compression, and that important properties of knowledge claims can be understood by measuring how well they compress information.

The ICT approach requires two conceptual shifts. The first, is to consider the magnitude and significance of scientific claims not in terms of ordinary metrics of effect size or significance, but in terms of the amount of information they convey. Put simply, the magnitude of reported effects, the theoretical relevance of results, the surprisingness of findings, the description of the methods and background theories and assumptions, and any other relevant aspect of a study is to be converted in the negative logarithm of a probability, in order to obtain the corresponding number of bits of information, also known as Shannon Entropy (see Cover and Thomas 2012).

The second, conceptual shift proposed by ICT is to consider knowledge claims as properties emerging from a "system", which comprises all the components that constitute the knowledge claim itself: the phenomena being studied, the measurements made on these phenomena, the theories formulated to explain them, the methods and procedures set in place to study them. Each of these components can be characterised in terms of variables, and relations between variables, and is therefore a "system" in the technical sense that it is a structure composed of interacting parts (the details of how to describe such a system will not be discussed in this paper, but more may be found in (Fanelli 2022, Fanelli et al. 2022)).

Such a system underlies both what we shall refer to as a "study" (intended as a single communicable knowledge claim, which is typically conveyed in a scientific publication) and a "field" (intended as a coherent literature addressing the same set of research questions) and it is partially, and in principle entirely, describable in terms of variables and relations between these variables.

The complexity of the system underlying a knowledge claim can be estimated by describing the system in terms of a graph – that is, a structure of concepts and relations – and then calculating combinatorially the number of possible graphs containing an equal or smaller number of concepts and relations. The logarithm of this number is the information needed to describe the system, which is also its Shannon Entropy. This concept of a system applies to studies as well fields. The only difference between the system underlying a

study and that underlying a field is that the latter is necessarily more complex, because its ensemble includes as subsets the ensembles of each study contributing to the field.

The central proposition of ICT is that, in order to compare knowledge claims with each other, we need to standardize the information yield of the system, dividing it by the total descriptive complexity of the system itself (Fanelli2019). This yields ICT's key quantity, K, measured as:

$$K = \frac{I}{D}$$

where

- I is the "Information yield" of the system, as it quantifies how much information is obtained about the explanandum (e.g. the answer to a research question).
- D is the "Descriptive complexity" of the system. Note that $D > 0$, with larger values indicating systems, including methods, of increasing complexity.

In other words, ICT claims that knowledge is quantified by a proportion, given by the ratio between the information (quantifying the predictive or explanatory power) yielded by the knowledge claim and the total information needed to describe the system within which this claim is made. Any knowledge-producing process strives to maximize K, and knowledge is obtained if and to the extent that:

$$K > 0 .$$

Therefore, based on the framework of ICT, this study propose that the problematic nature of any QRP may be quantified in terms of how much the QRP reduces the K value of a system.

2.3 Results

Applying the definition of QRP given above to the ICT framework, we obtained a first important result in the form of a simple mathematical rule that applies to individual studies as well as entire fields. Let us consider a study that is affected by a QRP. Based on our definition of QRP, this entails that the study's reported methods are simpler than the true methods, because the latter contain the additional QRP components that are not reported. Let D_t and D_b be, respectively, the incomplete and complete description of the study. The effect of the QRP is to potentially introduce a bias, which we can measure as a quantity, B , corresponding to the divergence between the "real" unbiased result I and the result reported by the study (technically, B is a Kullback-Leibler divergence, with $B > 0$). Since knowledge strives to be positive, we find that the knowledge yielded of the QRP-affected study is large to the extent that it satisfies the condition:

$$IR > B$$

in which $R = D_t/D_b$

is the study's *replicability*, term we shall use to indicate the extent to which the system underlying the knowledge claim can be replicated in subsequent studies. This term is not to be confused with the extent to which, when a study is replicated, the same results and conclusions are obtained, for which we might reserve the term *reproducibility* (see Voelkl and Würbel 2024). We have $0 < R < 1$, with lower values representing greater missing (and/or omitted) information, and therefore lesser capacity to repeat the exact same study.

The inequality above is a novel, but intuitive result, which connects to each other three variables of fundamental importance in research integrity and metascience. It mathematically states that the knowledge

yield is large to the extent that the bias is low (ideally, zero), whilst the information yield and the replicability are high. Conversely, the rule suggests that QRPs are problematic if and to the extent that they cause lower information yield (smaller I), lower replicability (smaller R), and higher bias (larger B). Note that, whilst we constructed this as an example of a "study", the same conclusion applies to a field (which is a just mixture of studies).

We then assessed how knowledge increases or decreases in a literature when a new study contributes to it, leading to a second general formula, which contextualises the impact of QRPs. We define the conditions in which a study makes a positive contribution to a field as those for which the K value of field+study is larger than that of the field alone. Conversely, the contribution is the K value of field+study is smaller than that of the field alone. It can be shown that the latter condition can be succinctly expressed as:

$$I(1 - i)R > B(1 - b)$$

in which I, R, B are, respectively, the information yield, replicability and bias of the field prior to including the study, and i, b quantify the relative impact that the study has on the information yield and bias of the field. These terms are functions of many variables but, without describing them in detail, for our purposes it suffices to note that $i > 1$ when the study increases the fields true information yield, and $b > 1$ when the study increases the biases of the field. In other words, i, b quantify in proportional terms the positive and negative contributions that a QRP-affected study makes to a QRP-affected field.

All else equal, this inequality suggests that a QRP-affected study will have a greater impact - positive or negative - in fields that have:

- Larger information yield (larger I). This characterises fields that, for example, study simpler phenomena, have higher theoretical and empirical consensus, and use more mature methodologies.
- Higher replicability (larger R). This characterises fields in which methods are more mature and better codified, have greater methodological consensus and higher transparency.
- Greater bias (larger B). This characterises fields in which QRPs or other factors already generate a systematic over- or under-estimation of the results, relative to what ought to be obtained by studies that use the theories and methodologies described by the fields.

Within such conditions, a QRP-affected study will have a more negative impact in proportion to how much it:

- Worsens the biases of the field (larger b). Conversely, if a study counters the biases of the field, then its impact is positive.
- Decreases (rather than increases) the information yield of the field (smaller I). This occurs when, for example, the quality of the study itself is lower even ignoring the QRP.
- Decreases the transparency (replicability) of the field. This occurs to the extent that the QRP-affect study is non transparent (it conceals the QRP) and the QRP itself is more unusual.

Furthermore, all else equal, this impact is greater for studies that have a greater influence of the field, for example when they have larger sample size, are published in high-impact journals, have highly influential authors.

To confirm these analytical results and gain further insights into how the variables interact with each other, we can calculate directly how much the K value of a literature (a field) changes when a study contributes to

it, under varying conditions of I, R and B values for study or field. Figure 2 shows the results of one such simulation. These simulations confirm the analytical conclusions above, by showing how, for the same level of bias and transparency of a study, the net K value changes most drastically under field conditions of high I,R and B (top right of the figure).

Figure 2: Simulation showing the net amount of knowledge acquired or lost by a literature (henceforth, a “field”) when a new study contributes to it, under varying conditions of I,R,B for field and study. Gradient colours represent the K value of the field calculated with the study minus the K value of the field without the study. Green represents a positive contribution of the study (K value of field+study is higher than field alone), and red a negative contribution. Calculations assume the explanandum is a binary (true/false) variable (e.g. whether an hypothesis is correct vs incorrect), were $P(Y=1)$ is the probability that the hypothesis is correct. Each individual heatmap shows how the net K value varies depending on the probability that the QRP-affected study ascribes to the hypothesis increase (x-axis, this affects the bias of the study) and as the about of information concealed increases (y-axis, showing the replicability R of the study). Vertical bars report the correct (green) and biased (red) field estimates of $P(Y=1)$. Each heat map is placed under different conditions of I, R, and B of the field. From left to right and top to bottom of each subset, heatmaps are placed under conditions of low, medium and high field values of information yield I, bias B, and replicability R, respectively. The study is assumed to have a weight of 0.5, i.e. to contribute exactly one half to the knowledge of the field.

2.4

Discussion

Our analysis sheds new light on the meaning of "context" and the importance this may have when evaluating to what extent what appears to be a results-related QRP is actually problematic. In particular, our analysis points to three fundamental dimensions that characterise the contexts of a literature to which a study contributes. These are:

- Information yield: this is the amount of knowledge that the literature is actually yielding, once corrected for its biases. A high information yield is found in fields that study simpler phenomena, using mature and well-codified theories and methods, with a high level of consensus.
- Replicability: this is the extent to which the studies characterising the field can actually be repeated, because all the necessary conditions, materials and actions are adequately reported in the studies' publications and can be implemented by others. This replicability is in part determined by factors that prescind QRPs (for example, fields that are less well-codified and phenomena that are more complex will have lower replicability). However, lack of transparency in reporting one's QRP is an independent, and for our purposes crucial cause of low replicability.
- Bias: this is the extent to which the results presented in a literature deviate systematically from those that would be obtained if the literature was free from QRPs. Note that these biases are directional, and they are most extreme when the biased results are in the opposite direction than the truth.

A direct estimation of the key inequalities advanced in this essay is presently beyond the practical reach of most researchers, administrators and policymakers interested in QRPs. However, an accurate estimation may be unnecessary for most uses, and simple heuristics and guiding principles may be sufficient to evaluate the context of a QRP in the real world. Table 2 reports a set of heuristic approaches to estimate the magnitude of these quantities and therefore to evaluate the context of a QRP.

Table 2: Heuristic approximations of the study or field variables in the analysis. Note that the same variables can refer to a study or a field. In the latter case, the quantities should be evaluated as averages and/or the combined beliefs of the literature produced by the field. In particular, field I and B are weighted mixtures of the corresponding probability distributions of each study, and R is the minimum set that contains as subsets the systems of all studies in the field. C represents the component of the description of a study that is not involved in the QRP and is therefore constant. The relative magnitude of C modulates the value of R. In particular, all else equal, the larger the C, the closer R is to the value of 1 and the less sensitive it will be to the hidden information. For example, in the “select data” case, if C is much larger than the sample size, then R is approximately 1 (the study is highly replicable); conversely, the larger the sample size is, the more R will approach the value of the ratio (declared sample size)/(original sample size).

Variable		Heuristic approximation						
Symbol	Short name	Definition	Select data	Select covariates	Select Analysis	Select results	Select publication	HARKing
I	Information yield	Information saved about the explanandum.	Magnitude of effect obtained without dropping data.	Magnitude of standardized coefficients obtained controlling for the covariates.	Substantive significance of the excluded analyses.	Substantive significance of the excluded results.	Substantive significance of the excluded publication.	Strength of support for hypothesis when tested ex-ante.
B	Bias	Divergence between information obtained with and without the QRP.	Divergence between effect with vs without dropped data.	Divergence between effect with vs without all covariates.	Divergence between results/conclusions of analyses reported vs omitted.	Divergence between results/conclusions of results reported vs omitted about the research question.	Divergence of results/conclusion about the research question with vs without the publication.	Divergence of conclusions about the hypothesis tested post-hoc vs ex-ante.
R	Replicability	Proportion of information describing the system that is documented and therefore in principle repeatable exactly.	$(C + \text{declared sample size}) / (C + \text{original sample size})$	$C / (C + \text{Number of models tested})$	$(C + \text{Number analyses presented}) / (C + \text{Number analyses performed})$	$(C + \text{Number results presented}) / (C + \text{Number results obtained})$	$(C + \text{Number published studies}) / (C + \text{Number unpublished studies})$	$(C + \text{Number hypotheses presented}) / (C + \text{Number hypotheses explored})$

Therefore, the nature and causes of the determinants of I,R,B,i,b and the extent to which these can be corrected are further important aspects of the context, that metascientists and policy-makers should take into account in their work.

These conclusions may have useful implications and applications for metascientists, research integrity investigators, and policy makers. A full examination and analysis of these implications is beyond the scope of this report, and this section will merely offer speculative suggestions, that a formal analysis might further assess in the future.

Metascientists might find these results useful to settle debates on whether QRPs like Selecting Publication or HARKing (e.g. Fiedler and Schwarz 2016, de Winter and Happee 2013, Rubin 2017) are problematic or not, because they introduce a formal and operationalizable definition of the "context" in which QRPs operate. Our results suggest that, as it often happens in debates on complex issues, both sides of the debate on QRPs are partially correct. On the one hand, a QRP is always problematic if taken out of context and evaluated individually, because by definition it reduces the amount of knowledge produced. On the other hand, the

epistemic effects of a QRP may quite obviously vary in magnitude and have upsides that, under the right conditions, can be positive for the field as a whole. Therefore, most QRPs entail a trade-off between positive and negative effects, and the net impact is bound to vary on a case-by-case basis and across contexts, as the magnitudes and causes of B,I,R vary for the study and for the field the study is contributing to.

Research integrity investigators might find in these results a framework to contextualise each particular allegation of scientific misconduct, helping to evaluate it with greater fairness and nuance. They can do so by referring to the heuristics in tables as a basis for their analyses, thus taking into account contextual factors including the level of maturity and codification of the field, the average strength of its evidence, its existing biases etc.

Policymakers may gain from this analysis a tool to assess what problems need prioritizing and how best to tackle them in different contexts (e.g. fields, research cultures, institutions). In particular, a plausible implication of these results is that policies aimed at correcting or punishing individual behaviours may be more justified and effective in high-information, high-replicability, low-bias contexts. Conversely, in contexts characterised by low information yield (that is, noise or uncertainty about theories and findings), low replicability, and high bias, policy efforts might more profitably be direct at improving the conditions of the context itself, for example by improving a field's theoretical quality, methodological rigour and reporting standards.

3 Do researchers evaluate Questionable Research Practices based on the context? Insights from a large-scale experiment on HARKing

As already pointed out above, the actual prevalence and impact of QRPs is a matter of significant controversy. An extensive theoretical literature suggests that QRPs may not always be a significant problem, depending on the context.

One of the QRPs whose impact has been most thoroughly scrutinised is known as HARKing – acronym that indicates the act of “Hypothesizing After Results are Known” (Kerr 1998). In its most typical form, HARKing occurs when a researcher formulates a hypothesis to explain its findings after observing them and then presents the study as a test (and confirmation) of that hypothesis. This behaviour is believed to introduce a bias in the literature, because it might induce an over-estimation of the strength of evidence in favour of the post-hoc derived hypothesis, by making exploratory results appear as confirmatory (Lishner 2021). However, several arguments have been advanced to suggest that, under the right conditions, HARKing might be a minor problem, or it might be even beneficial, as it allows results to be presented in a more concise and informative way (Rubin 2017, Vancouver 2018). This line of reasoning points out that the distorting effect of HARKing is maximal when the post-hoc hypothesis is completely and idiosyncratically invoked to explain the results observed, whereas it is minimised to the extent that the post-hoc hypothesis is generated from rigorous theoretical reasoning and in line with theories and evidence that pre-exist the results observed. The most extreme such case occurs when the post-hoc hypothesis is generated entirely independently of the data observed, which may occur if the hypothesis was not “formulated” by the researcher but rather re-discovered in the literature – a special condition defined as “RHARKing” or “Retrieving a Hypothesis After Results are Known” (Rubin 2017).

Do researchers take this theory into account when evaluating the ethical standing of a QRP and consider engaging with it? Taking HARKing as an example of a potentially context-dependent QRP, we conducted a pre-registered (<https://osf.io/wzg83>) online experiment to assess whether varying contextual factors changed researchers' perceptions and justifications for HARKing.

We tested five contextual factors that may modulate the severity of HARKing. These comprise the RHARKing vs HARKing distinction discussed above, and four additional contextual factors, which we derived from a preliminary version of the theoretical framework reported in section 4. Our experiment tested hypotheses concerning the influence of following contextual factors:

1. HARKing type: in line with the literature reviewed above, we hypothesised that a “pure” form of HARKing, in which the post-hoc hypothesis is derived entirely idiosyncratically, might be perceived to be more harmful than RHARKing, in which the hypothesis is retrieved from the literature (Rubin 2017).

2. Extent of selectivity: All else equal, the plausibility of a post-hoc derived hypothesis is inversely related to the number of possible hypotheses it was derived from. A greater selectivity affects directly the replicability (R) variable discussed in section 4 (see Table 2). Therefore, we hypothesised that both HARKing and RHARKing might be judged more severely when the post-hoc hypothesis accommodates one of a larger number of possible results.

3. Sample size of the study: all else equal, the consequences of HARKing (and any QRP) are more severe for studies that are most influential and of higher quality. A larger sample size increases both the “i” and “b” variables discussed in the section 4. Since sample size is one of the factors that make a study more influential, we hypothesised that researchers might be more reluctant to engage in HARKing within a study with a large

sample. Moreover, a study with a larger sample size might be perceived as intrinsically of higher quality and relevance, reducing the value or interest of post-hoc hypothesising.

4. Size of the literature: we hypothesised that the perception of HARKing might be modulated by the size of the body of literature to which a HARKing-affected study contributes, based on two plausible theoretical considerations. First, the impact of a QRP-affected study might be perceived as less severe in a large field, where its distorting effects will be relatively minor (that is, smaller “*I*” and “*b*” values in the analysis above). Second, a larger body of literature yields a broader pool of prior hypotheses and evidence, from which the post-hoc hypothesis might be derived and needs to align itself with. The direction of this effect might be modulated by the level of theoretical consensus, discussed below.

5. Level of theoretical consensus in the field: post-hoc hypotheses are by definition less theoretically constrained in fields with low theoretical consensus. Fields with lower theoretical consensus have a lower information yield and lower replicability (*I*, *R* in the analysis of section 2). Therefore, we hypothesised that HARKing might be perceived as less problematic in fields with lower theoretical consensus.

To evaluate the effects of these factors on researchers' perception of HARKing, we conducted an online experiment where participants read a research scenario developed following the best practices of vignette studies (Aguinis & Bradley, 2014). A similar methodology has been successfully applied in the context of studying the accuracy of reporting of scientific findings (Allard & Clavier, 2023). All participants were PhD holders' graduate students (~6% of the sample due to mismatch with Prolific inclusion criteria). The vignette each participant read was identical except for words that represented 2 levels of the 5 contextual factors (Figure 1). The vignette was sampled out of 32 between-subject conditions and described a particular combination of 5 contextual factor levels.

After reading the vignette, participants were sequentially presented with 2 summaries reflecting inferences that could be drawn from the research scenario. Participants had to indicate the degree to which they would 1) use the respective summary of the research results (intention) 2) consider the summary to be an accurate reflection of the findings (perceived validity) 3) think that other researchers in their field would use the summary (perceived norm) 4) think that the respective summary could increase the probability that a scientific paper gets published (publishability). The responses were reported on a scale from 1 (Completely disagree) to 9 (Completely agree) (see Methods for a more detailed description of the procedure). We analysed the effects of contextual factors on each question to evaluate whether these contextual factors modulate researchers' perception of QRP. We also asked participating researchers to explicitly evaluate the extent to which they think the contextual factors influence the impact of HARKing on scientific field.

3.1

Methods

We used Prolific academic to recruit academic researchers from different fields. Our final effective sample size was $N=1474$, 52.4% of whom were female, 46.9% male, and remaining 0.7% unspecified (Other & Prefer not to). We also included 6% of participants who reported being a graduate student in the final sample. Overall, the sample consisted of a diverse group of participants across various demographics, professional positions, and research fields. While the majority were in the 25–35 age range and identified as researchers in psychology or biology, a significant portion also worked in industry or other fields.

"Imagine that you are a researcher studying the physiological basis of human movement. You are using a previously collected dataset, which includes 5 / 25 (Selection space) different parameters measuring motor performance, and its sample size is large / small (Sample size) by the standards of the research field.

You focus on the relationship between metabolic rate and motor performance which is a poorly explored question, with only a few existing studies / a well-explored question, with dozens of existing studies (Well-exploredness). Hypotheses about this relationship are mostly in agreement / in conflict (Consensus). Based on available theorizing, you hypothesize that metabolic rate should have a positive correlation with hand coordination. You conduct the analysis testing this hypothesis and find no statistically significant association. However, having looked at all available measures, you find that the metabolic rate has a statistically significant positive correlation with motor reaction time.

This makes sense, because thinking about it, it seems plausible to hypothesize / searching through the literature, you find an old article hypothesizing (R vs pure HARKing) that metabolic rate would predict reaction times."

HARKing summary: Understanding the physiological basis of human movement is critical to developing new diagnostic tools and clinical interventions. To this end, the current research investigated how heart rate influences fine motor skills. The hypothesis that heart rate is positively correlated with finger tapping speed was tested and the results supported the hypothesis. The results also suggested that heart rate is not associated with grip strength.

Non-HARKing summary: Understanding the physiological basis of human movement is critical to developing new diagnostic tools and clinical interventions. To this end, the current research investigated how heart rate influences fine motor skills. The hypothesis that heart rate is positively correlated with grip strength was tested but the results did not support the hypothesis. In exploratory analyses it was found that heart rate is significantly associated with finger tapping speed.

Figure 3: Design and procedure of the experiment (panel A) and text of the vignette and summary used (panel B).

The procedure of the experiment is described in Figure 3A. Participating researchers first had to read a vignette (shown in Figure 3B) describing a research scenario which they subsequently had to summarize in 3 sentences. Summarizing was used to increase processing depth of the scenario, and the written response was also later used as a data quality check. In combination with other data quality checks (attention checks, speeding), we excluded a total of 410 participants (21%) from the initial sample 1884. They then proceeded to evaluate two summaries describing main research findings of the scenario along 4 outcome measures. The first summary reflected HARKing, as it hid the fact that initial hypothesis was changed, whereas the second summary was transparent regarding the initial hypothesis. We varied 5 contextual factors in a between-subject manner to avoid generating explicit contrasts between two levels of the factor for researchers. Participants were randomly assigned to one of 32 different versions of the research scenario.

3.2 Results

Figure 4. Effects of contextual factors on perception of HARKing. Contextual factors are distinguished by colour. In this plot y-axis of each of the 4 subplots represents one key outcome measured of the study (Intention to use the summary, perceived validity of the summary, perceived norm of whether other researchers would use the summary and perceived publishability of the summary). Within each panel the two subplots represent effects for HARKing vs non-HARKing summary separately. On the x-axes, 2 levels of each contextual factor are presented side-by-side.

Figure 4 summarises the main result of the experiment. On average, participants gave the HARKing summary a lower score than the non-HARKing one along all four dimensions measured - in other words, participants

reported significantly lower intention to engage in HARKing, lower perceived scientific validity, and lower perceived publishability for HARKing summaries compared to non-HARKing. This suggests that, in general researchers perceived HARKing as a less appropriate or desirable practice. Manipulating the contextual factors had very little effect on these scores, suggesting that participants' perception of HARKing were not significantly affected by the variability of contextual factors in the experiment. A marginal exception was observed for sample size, which was significantly associated with a reduction in the intention to engage in HARKing, and for extent of selectivity, which was negatively associated with the perceived scientific validity of HARKing (Figure 4). Both these effects are aligned with theoretical predictions, but are substantially small in magnitude and, if corrected for the multiple comparisons run in our analyses, would not pass conventional thresholds of statistical significance. Overall, therefore, we conclude that our manipulation of contextual factors did not substantially alter the reported perception of HARKing.

However, we found that the field and career level of researchers significantly modulated their perception of HARKing. Social scientists reported significantly lower intentions to use HARKing compared to researchers in other fields, with the largest difference observed between social and physical sciences. Additionally, PhD students exhibited the highest intention to use HARKing summary, whereas full professors and post-PhD researchers reported the lowest intention. Both researcher field and position also moderated the effect of selection space, indicating that disciplinary and career-stage differences shape how researchers respond to contextual factors.

Prior knowledge of HARKing was also an important modulating factor. Whilst general prior knowledge of QRPs did not significantly influence HARKing intentions, researchers who self-reported having greater knowledge of HARKing reported lower intentions to use HARKing summaries. Similarly, perceived harmfulness of HARKing significantly moderated intention to HARK, with lower intentions to engage in HARKing among those who considered it more harmful.

Most importantly, however, prior beliefs concerning the contextual sensitivity of HARKing modulated the perception of HARKing itself. In particular, the more participants agreed that a contextual factor moderated the impact of HARKing, to higher the score they gave to HARKing, along all dimensions (Figure 5).

The impact of HARKing depends on...
(1 - Completely disagree, 9 - Completely agree)

Summary Type ● HARKing Summary ● Non-HARKing Summary

Figure 5. Intention to HARK is related to beliefs about the contextual nature of HARKing. Explicit beliefs about contextual factors moderate intention to use the HARKing vs non-HARKing summary. Each panel reports the average intention scores given by participants to the HARKing (green) and non-HARKing (red) summary, partitioned by their level of agreement that a given contextual factor modulated the impact of HARKing. The more participants agreed that HARKing depended on that contextual factor, the higher was their willingness to use the HARKing summary.

3.3 Summary and Discussion

Our experiment assessed whether and how the relative perception of a HARKing summary would be altered by contextual factors that are theoretically understood to modulate the gravity HARKing and other QRPs.

We found that researchers rated a HARKing summary as generally less desirable and inferior to a non-HARKing (i.e. a fully transparent and accurate) summary, suggesting that they understand HARKing to be a suboptimal and potentially problematic practice.

Our manipulation of factors made a very small, and substantially non-significant difference to this pattern. This could suggest that researchers' perceptions of HARKing and other QRPs are not significantly affected by the context, although we cannot exclude those limitations in our experimental design made it insufficiently sensitive to measure these effects. In particular, participants were only shown one version of each vignette,

with a unique combination of variables, that in most cases varied very subtly (e.g. going from 5 to 25 variables, or stating “few” vs “several”, etc.). These may be too subtle cues to make a measurable difference in this cross-sectional, between-subject experimental set-up. In support of the latter hypothesis, we observed that most differences in scores, whilst generally non-significant, were mostly in the direction predicted theoretically. It is therefore possible that a different study design would be able to detect the predicted differences with greater magnitude.

Indeed, whilst the contextual factors didn't exert a significant direct effect on the perception of HARKing, we found that researchers varied in their beliefs about whether contextual factors mattered, and their beliefs significantly altered their perception of HARKing. In other words, researchers who, in agreement with several theories, believe that HARKing is context-dependent are less averse to a HARKed summary, presumably because they perceive it less generally problematic. However, even these researchers still rate a transparent summary as equal or preferable (Figure 5).

Prior knowledge and experience about HARKing also made a significant difference, as evidenced by the lower propensity to use HARKing reported by researchers who were more senior, who believed HARKing to be most harmful, and who worked in the social sciences, where the discussion of QRPs has been more extensive. Intriguingly, general knowledge of QRPs did not have the same modulating effect, suggesting that the perception of the gravity of a given QRP is modulated not by a general understanding of QRPs, but rather by the specific understanding of that particular QRP – HARKing, in this case.

Therefore, results of this experiment suggest that the level of knowledge and understanding that researchers have about QRPs is a crucial factor that determines their likelihood to engage with them, and highlight the importance of developing and disseminating a clearer understanding of the impact of QRPs and, where this impact is context-dependent, a more nuanced understanding of the conditions that make that QRP more or less problematic.

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